

1 **Fezf1 is a novel autoimmune regulator.**

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7 The most classically described autoimmune regulator is AIRE, which activates transcription of genes
8 known as tissue-restricted antigens (TRA), like insulin and tyrosine hydroxylase, in a process known as
9 promiscuous gene expression (PGE). TRA activation in the cortical cells of the medulla of the thymus
10 (mTEC) functions to present “self” to developing lymphocytes (B and T cells) for negative selection of
11 autoreactive cells during lymphocyte development. We showed that MHC-II is required for this process.
12 We demonstrate here that the zinc finger nuclear factor Fezf1 functions as an autoimmune regulator,
13 controlling the expression of select TRA as well as a group of genes functioning in tolerance and self
14 non-self recognition in the immune system.

15 Citations

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